

Machine learning discoveries of METTL3-X synergy in ETC-1922159 treated colorectal cancer cells

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Abstract

Methyltransferase 3, N⁶-adenosine-methyltransferase complex catalytic subunit (METTL3) is the most studied member of the METTL protein family and is located on the human chromosome 14q11.2. METTL3 belong to a sub-family of seven-beta-strand (7BS) methyltransferases which the function by the most prevalent and reversible internal methylation (i.e m⁶A modification) of their substrates like mRNA, tRNA, pri-mRNA, lncRNA, snRNA, rRNA, miRNA. It has been found to be in elevated levels in various cancer types. In colorectal cancer (CRC) cells treated with ETC-1922159, METTL3 was found to be down regulated along with other genes. A recently developed search engine ranked combinations of METTL3-X (X, a particular gene/protein) at 2nd order level after drug administration. Some of these combinations have been tested in wet lab, however many have been pointed out by the search engine that are yet to be explored/tested. These rankings reveal which METTL3-X combinations might be working synergistically in CRC. In this research work, I cover combinations of METTL3 with members of NIMA (never in mitosis gene a)-related kinase (NEK), v-myc avian myelocytomatosis viral oncogene homolog (MYC), Epstein-Barr nuclear antigen (EBNA), enhancer of zeste homolog 2 (EHZ2), autophagy related (ATG), chromobox homolog (CBX), DEAD-box helicase (DDX), DNA methyltransferase (DNMT), E2F transcription factor (E2F), EpsteinBarr virus nuclear antigen (EBNA), F-box protein (FBX), high mobility group (HMG), heterogeneous nuclear ribonucleoprotein (HNRNP), homeobox (HOX), integrin subunits (ITG), interleukin (IL), kinesin family member (KIF), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA (LINC), poly(ADP-ribose) polymerase (PARP), RNA binding motif protein (RBM), solute carrier family 7 member (SLC7), small nucleolar RNA host gene (SNHG), transcription factor (TCF), transforming growth factor beta (TGFB), tripartite motif containing (TRIM), ubiquitin conjugating enzyme E2 (UBE2), ubiquitin specific peptidase (USP), zinc finger and BTB domain containing (ZBTB) and zinc finger protein (ZNF) family.

*ML discoveries of METTL3-X synergy in ETC-1922159 treated CRC cells

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1. Introduction

1.1. METTL3

Modified nucleosides are present in mRNA of all eukaryotes, though at much lower levels than in other RNA moieties such as rRNA, tRNA, and snRNA. Modification by methylation occurs on the terminal guanosine of the cap (N⁷-methylguanosine), and the first two encoded nucleosides (2'-O-methylnucleosides) in most higher eukaryotes. Modification by methylation also occurs at internal adenosine residues in many species (N⁶-methyladenosine). Modification by deamination occurs at specific adenosine and cytidine residues in very specific cases leading to post-transcriptional editing. Studies have shown the importance of the cap N⁷-methylguanosine however the role of the 2'-O-methylnucleosides is not as well understood. In their review, Bokar [1] focused on the role of internal N⁶-methyladenosine residues. The formation of N⁶-methyladenosine is catalyzed by a complex enzyme containing a subunit (MT-A70) that co-localizes with nuclear speckles and appears to be widely expressed in all higher eukaryotes. Jia et al. [2] indicate that the discovery of at least two m⁶A demethylases FTO (Jia et al. [3]) and ALKBH5 (Zheng et al. [4]) proteins, point that this modification is reversible and regulated, thus playing a role biological regulation.

Methyltransferase-like (METTL) family of proteins play critical roles in this RNA modification, thus methylating various types of RNAs. They consist of a unique 7BS domain, which binds to the methyl donor SAM to catalyze methyl transfer. In a recent review, Qi et al. [5] provide a detailed survey of the METTL family including expression of METTLs in human cancer, their mechanisms of up/down regulation in cancer, their roles in proliferation, invasion, metastasis, reprogramming of tumor cell metabolism, tumor immune response, tumor chemotherapy, their diagnostic value and prognosis evaluation in cancer and the recent developments of molecular inhibitors of METTLs.

Liu et al. [6] discovered methyltransferase METTL14 that forms a stable heterodimer with METTL3 that performs m⁶A deposition/modification on nuclear RNA inside mammalian cells. Further, WTAP interacts with the METTL3-14 complex to affect the cellular m⁶A deposition. They provide a schematic illustration for the reversible methylation of N⁶-adenosine in RNA through METTL3-14 complex and the m⁶A RNA demethylases.

Zeng et al. [7] summarize current understanding regarding the oncogenic and tumor-suppressive functions of METTL3, as well as the underlying molecular mechanisms. They also discuss the protein structure of the METTL3-14 heterodimer that provides the basis for potential therapeutic targeting. In a later review Jin et al. [8], discuss factors that regulate METTL3 expression and explores the specific mechanisms by which METTL3 affects multiple tumor biological behaviors, with the aim to provide fundamental support for tumor diagnosis and treatment and offer new ideas for the development of tumor-targeting drugs.

In an observational study, Li et al. [9] showed that METTL3 expression level was significantly upregulated in CRC tissues, and its high expression was closely related to a variety of adverse clinico-pathological features of CRC. In CRC cells treated with ETC-1922159, METTL3 was found to be down regulated along with other genes. Some combinations of METTL3 have been confirmed in wet lab, however, many of the combinations have not been explored/tested or are known. To reveal these combinations, I use a modification of a recently published machine learning based search engine, details of which are given in the next section.

1.2. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [10], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Readers are requested to go through the adaptation of the above mentioned work for gaining deeper insight into the working of the pipeline and its use of published data set generated after administration of ETC-1922159, Sinha [11]. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [12] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations.

2. Results & Discussion

2.1. METTL3 related synergies

2.1.1. METTL3 - NEK / MYC / EBNA / EZH2

In cervical cancer (CC), Guo et al. [13] observed upregulation of METTL3 and identified NEK2 as a target of METTL3 in CC cells. Their analysis showed that METTL3 regulated NEK2 expression through m⁶A modification and mediated the malignant phenotype of CC cells. Similarly, Ma et al. [14] showed that knockdown of METTL3 reduced CC cell proliferation and regulated expression of MYC by identifying m⁶A-modified MYC. EpsteinBarr virus (EBV) infects a human B lymphocyte and Zheng et al. [15] found that EBV EBNA2 was highly m⁶A-modified upon EBV infection. Knockdown of METTL3 decreased EBNA2 expression levels, thus showing mechanistic connection between METTL3 and EBNA2. In lung cancer tissues, Chen et al. [16] found that METTL3 and EZH2 levels were upregulated. Their levels, as well as cell proliferative and metastatic abilities, were dose-dependently inhibited in Simvastatin-induced A549 cells. They observed that METTL3 positively regulated EZH2 level, and m⁶A modification on its mRNA. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with METTL3. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these individual members, and METTL3, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these individual members along with METTL3.

Table 1 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 2 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1. The table 1 shows rankings of these individual members w.r.t METTL3. NEK2 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 171 (linear) and 202 (rbf). MYC - METTL3 shows low ranking

of 823 (linear) and 1469 (rbf). EBNA1BP2 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 715 (laplace) and 1260 (rbf). EZH2 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1339 (laplace), 1374 (linear) and 1094 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS METTL3			
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T METTL3			
	laplace	linear	rbf
NEK2 - METTL3	2171	171	202
MYC - METTL3	2651	823	1469
EBNA1BP2 - METTL3	715	2155	1260
EZH2 - METTL3	1339	1374	1094

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between METTL3 VS Individual members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 graphically, with the following influences - • individual members w.r.t METTL3 with METTL3 – > NEK2 / MYC / EBNA1BP2 / EZH2.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
Individual members w.r.t METTL3	
NEK2	METTL3
MYC	METTL3
EBNA1BP2	METTL3
EZH2	METTL3

Table 2: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between METTL3 and individual members.

2.1.2. METTL3 - ATG

Ischemia/reperfusion (I/R) injury is a severe brain disorder and Yu et al. [17] utilized a middle cerebral artery occlusion (MCAO) rat model and SH-SY5Y cells subjected to oxygen-glucose deprivation/reoxygenation (OGD/R) to assess m⁶A levels and investigate the impact of METTL3 overexpression on long non-coding RNA (lncRNA) CRNDE expression. METTL3 overexpression inhibited lncRNA CRNDE expression which mitigated OGD/R-induced apoptosis and inflammation in SH-SY5Y cells, while

enhancing autophagy and stabilizing ATG10 mRNA. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with METTL3. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these ATG members, and METTL3, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these ATG members along with METTL3.

Table 3 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 4 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 3. The table 3 shows rankings of ATG members w.r.t METTL3. ATG3 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 172 (laplace) and 1065 (rbf). ATG10 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 381 (laplace), 1491 (linear) and 726 (rbf). ATG4C - METTL3 shows low ranking of 404 (laplace), 268 (linear) and 304 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

RANKING ATG MEMBERS VS METTL3			
RANKING OF ATG MEMBERS W.R.T METTL3			
	laplace	linear	rbf
ATG3 - METTL3	172	2205	1065
ATG10 - METTL3	381	1491	726
ATG4C - METTL3	404	268	304

Table 3: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between METTL3 VS ATG members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 3 graphically, with the following influences - • ATG members w.r.t METTL3 with METTL3 – > ATG-3/10/4C.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
ATG members w.r.t METTL3	
ATG-3/10/4C	METTL3

Table 4: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between METTL3 and ATG members.

2.1.3. METTL3 - CBX

In osteosarcoma metastasis, Huo et al. [18] found that METTL3 binds to the mRNA of regulatory protein CBX4 and regulates the mRNA and protein expression of CBX4. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with METTL3. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159,

these CBX members, and METTL3, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these CBX members along with METTL3.

Table 5 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 6 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 5. The table 5 shows rankings of CBX members w.r.t METTL3. CBX3 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 887 (laplace) and 782 (rbf). CBX5 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1542 (laplace), 1138 (linear) and 221 (rbf). CBX2 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 145 (linear) and 42 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, CBX1 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with METTL3, before treatment.

RANKING CBX MEMBERS VS METTL3			
RANKING OF CBX MEMBERS W.R.T METTL3			
	laplace	linear	rbf
CBX3 - METTL3	887	1797	782
CBX5 - METTL3	1542	1138	221
CBX1 - METTL3	1952	1344	2325
CBX2 - METTL3	2097	145	42

Table 5: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between METTL3 VS CBX members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 5 graphically, with the following influences - • CBX members w.r.t METTL3 with METTL3 – > CBX-3/5/2.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
CBX members w.r.t METTL3	
CBX-3/5/2	METTL3

Table 6: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between METTL3 and CBX members.

2.1.4. METTL3 - DDX

Zhao et al. [19] found that human DDX5 promotes replication of influenza virus in A549 cells. Mechanistically, DDX5 was found to downregulate the antiviral transcripts via the METTL3-METTL14/YTHDF2 axis. These experimental studies confirm the

existence of synergy between the above involved factors with METTL3. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these DDX members, and METTL3, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these DDX members along with METTL3.

Table 7 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 8 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 7. The table 7 shows rankings of DDX members w.r.t METTL3. DDX31 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 195 (laplace), 1247 (linear) and 289 (rbf). DDX21 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 326 (laplace) and 1296 (rbf). DDX55 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1032 (laplace), 882 (linear) and 614 (rbf). DDX46 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1119 (laplace), 460 (linear) and 566 (rbf). DDX56 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1157 (laplace), 875 (linear) and 867 (rbf). DDX11 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1203 (laplace), 765 (linear) and 396 (rbf). DDX20 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1250 (laplace), 1039 (linear) and 1159 (rbf). DDX51 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1390 (laplace), 1516 (linear) and 1146 (rbf). DDX12P - METTL3 shows low ranking of 242 (linear) and 140 (rbf). DDX27 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1254 (linear) and 467 (rbf). DDX10 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 641 (linear) and 762 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, DDX28, DDX19A, DDX18 and DDX54 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with METTL3, before treatment.

RANKING DDX MEMBERS VS METTL3							
RANKING OF DDX MEMBERS W.R.T METTL3							
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
DDX31 - METTL3	195	1247	289	DDX21 - METTL3	326	2516	1296
DDX28 - METTL3	632	1683	2002	DDX19A - METTL3	880	1648	1921
DDX55 - METTL3	1032	882	614	DDX46 - METTL3	1119	460	566
DDX56 - METTL3	1157	875	867	DDX11 - METTL3	1203	765	396
DDX20 - METTL3	1250	1039	1159	DDX51 - METTL3	1390	1516	1146
DDX18 - METTL3	1862	1512	2477	DDX12P - METTL3	2156	242	140
DDX27 - METTL3	2450	1254	467	DDX10 - METTL3	2585	641	762
DDX54 - METTL3	2733	1951	713				

Table 7: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between METTL3 VS DDX members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 7 graphically, with the following influences - • DDX members w.r.t METTL3 with METTL3 – > DDX-31/21/55/46/56/11/20/51/12P/27/10.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

DDX members w.r.t METTL3

DDX-31/21/55/46/56/11/20/51/12P/27/10 METTL3

Table 8: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between METTL3 and DDX members.

2.1.5. METTL3 - DNMT

Tang et al. [20] revealed that m⁶A modification of IGFBP7-OT promoted osteoarthritis (OA) progression by regulating the DNMT1/DNMT3A-IGFBP7 axis. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with METTL3. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these DNMT members, and METTL3, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these DNMT members along with METTL3.

Table 9 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 10 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 9. The table 9 shows rankings of DNMT members w.r.t METTL3. DNMT3A - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1198 (laplace), 863 (linear) and 757 (rbf). DNMT1 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 621 (linear) and 412 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, DNMT3B showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with METTL3, before treatment.

RANKING DNMT MEMBERS VS METTL3			
RANKING OF DNMT MEMBERS W.R.T METTL3			
	laplace	linear	rbf
DNMT3A - METTL3	1198	863	757
DNMT3B - METTL3	2244	2031	2622
DNMT1 - METTL3	2504	621	412

Table 9: 2nd order interaction ranking between METTL3 VS DNMT members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 9 graphically, with the following influences - • DNMT members w.r.t METTL3 with METTL3 – > DNMT-3A/1.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
DNMT members w.r.t METTL3	
DNMT-3A/1	METTL3

Table 10: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between METTL3 and DNMT members.

2.1.6. METTL3 - E2F

Tang et al. [21] found that METTL3 was highly expressed in pancreatic cancer and E2F5 was found to be positively regulated by METTL3. Downregulation of METTL3 restrained the viability, migration and invasion of pancreatic cancer cells and silencing METTL3 resulted in the decreased stability of E2F5 by methylating E2F5. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with METTL3. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these E2F members, and METTL3, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these E2F members along with METTL3.

Table 11 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 12 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 11. The table 11 shows rankings of E2F members w.r.t METTL3. E2F8 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1147 (laplace), 280 (linear) and 677(rbf). E2F5 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1438 (laplace) and 1309 (rbf). E2F7 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 603 (linear) and 600 (rbf). E2F1 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 551 (linear) and 577 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, E2F2 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with METTL3, before treatment.

RANKING E2F MEMBERS VS METTL3			
RANKING OF E2F MEMBERS W.R.T METTL3			
	laplace	linear	rbf
E2F8 - METTL3	1147	280	677
E2F5 - METTL3	1438	1850	1309
E2F2 - METTL3	1455	2415	2052
E2F7 - METTL3	2183	603	600
E2F1 - METTL3	2564	551	577

Table 11: 2nd order interaction ranking between METTL3 VS E2F members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 11 graphically, with the following influences - • E2F members w.r.t METTL3 with METTL3 – > E2F-8/5/7/1.

2.1.7. METTL3 -FBX

In pancreatic cancer (PC) patients, Chen et al. [22] found that FBXO31 was overexpressed, leading to promotion of tumor growth. Mechanistically, SIRT2 was a target of

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

E2F members w.r.t METTL3
E2F-8/5/7/1 **METTL3**

Table 12: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between METTL3 and E2F members.

and interacted with, FBXO31 and the latter promoted proteasome-dependent degradation of SIRT2 while binding to it. SIRT2 was found to be required for the oncogenic role of FBXO31 in PC progression. METTL3 induced m⁶A modification of FBXO31 and up-regulated FBXO31 expression, subsequently leading to SIRT2 down-regulation in PC cells and tumorigenesis. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with METTL3. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these FBX members, and METTL3, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these FBX members along with METTL3.

Table 13 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 14 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 13. The table 13 shows rankings of FBX members w.r.t METTL3. FBXO5 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 79 (linear) and 307 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, FBXL8, FBXO4, FBXO41 and FBXW9 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with METTL3, before treatment.

RANKING FBX MEMBERS VS METTL3

RANKING OF FBX MEMBERS W.R.T METTL3

	laplace	linear	rbf
FBXO5 - METTL3	1622	79	307
FBXL8 - METTL3	1902	2370	1432
FBXO4 - METTL3	2298	2647	2677
FBXO41 - METTL3	2308	2060	1492
FBXW9 - METTL3	2709	2348	1947

Table 13: 2nd order interaction ranking between METTL3 VSFBX members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 13 graphically, with the following influences - • FBX members w.r.t METTL3 with METTL3 – > FBX-O5.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

FBX members w.r.t METTL3

FBX-O5	METTL3
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Table 14: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between METTL3 and FBX members.

2.1.8. METTL3 -HMG

Subretinal fibrosis (SF) is a major cause of the poor visual prognosis for patients with neovascular age-related macular degeneration (nAMD) and myofibroblasts originated from retinal pigment epithelial (RPE) cells through epithelialmesenchymal transition (EMT) contribute to the fibrosis formation. m⁶A modification has been implicated in the EMT process and multiple fibrotic diseases. Wang et al. [23] in their study, found that during SF in the mouse model, METTL3 was upregulated in RPE cells and HMGA2 was identified as a downstream target of METTL3, which activated potent EMT-inducing transcription factor SNAIL. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with METTL3. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these HMG members, and METTL3, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these HMG members along with METTL3.

Table 15 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 16 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 15. The table 15 shows rankings of HMG members w.r.t METTL3. HMGB3 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 259 (laplace), 1300 (linear) and 891 (rbf). HMGB2 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 161 (linear) and 170 (rbf). HMGN2 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 336 (linear) and 612 (rbf). HMGN3 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 220 (linear) and 28 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, HMGB1 and HMGN5 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with METTL3, before treatment.

One can also interpret the results of the table 15 graphically, with the following influences - • HMG members w.r.t METTL3 with METTL3 – > HMG-B3/B2/N2/N3.

2.1.9. METTL3 -HNRNP

Kwon et al. [24] observed that METTL3 is required for m⁶A RNA methylation and HNRNP-A2/B1 localization during mouse preimplantation development. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with METTL3. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these HNRNP members, and METTL3, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these HNRNP members along with METTL3.

Table 17 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unex-

RANKING HMG MEMBERS VS METTL3			
RANKING OF HMG MEMBERS W.R.T METTL3			
	laplace	linear	rbf
HMGB3 - METTL3	259	1300	891
HMGB1 - METTL3	2044	1389	2558
HMGB2 - METTL3	2076	161	170
HMGN2 - METTL3	2099	336	612
HMGN5 - METTL3	2380	2135	2730
HMGN3 - METTL3	2506	220	28

Table 15: 2nd order interaction ranking between METTL3 VS HMG members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
HMG members w.r.t METTL3	
HMG-B3/B2/N2/N3	METTL3

Table 16: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between METTL3 and HMG members.

explored combinatorial hypotheses in table 18 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 17. The table 17 shows rankings of HNRNP members w.r.t METTL3. HNRNPA3 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 865 (laplace), 792 (linear) and 128 (rbf). HNRNPR - METTL3 shows low ranking of 934 (laplace) and 1392 (linear). HNRNPC - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1345 (laplace), 1234 (linear) and 1276 (rbf). HNRNPA1 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1414 (laplace), 1170 (linear) and 874 (rbf). HNRNPD - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1050 (linear) and 797 (rbf). HNRNPM - METTL3 shows low ranking of 293 (linear) and 958 (rbf). HNRNPA0 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1098 (linear) and 1442 (rbf). HNRNPH3 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 261 (linear) and 945 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, HNRNPA1L2 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with METTL3, before treatment.

One can also interpret the results of the table 17 graphically, with the following influences - ● HNRNP members w.r.t METTL3 with METTL3 - > HNRNPA3/R/C/A1/D/M/A0/H3.

RANKING HNRNP MEMBERS VS METTL3			
RANKING OF HNRNP MEMBERS W.R.T METTL3			
	laplace	linear	rbf
HNRNPA1L2 - METTL3	694	2089	1793
HNRNPA3 - METTL3	865	792	128
HNRNPR - METTL3	934	1392	1888
HNRNPC - METTL3	1345	1234	1276
HNRNPA1 - METTL3	1414	1170	874
HNRNPD - METTL3	1771	1050	797
HNRNPM - METTL3	2039	293	958
HNRNPA0 - METTL3	2391	1098	1442
HNRNPH3 - METTL3	2577	261	945

Table 17: 2nd order interaction ranking between METTL3 VS HNRNP members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
HNRNP members w.r.t METTL3	
HNRNP-A3/R/C/A1/D/M/A0/H3	METTL3

Table 18: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between METTL3 and HNRNP members.

2.1.10. METTL3 - HOX/ITG

Congenital pseudarthrosis of the tibia (CPT) is a health challenge in pediatric orthopedics. The essential process in the development of CPT is the limited capacity of mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) derived from CPT to undergo osteogenic differentiation. Ye et al. [25] found that METTL3 overexpression enhanced CPT MSCs' osteogenic differentiation and stabilized HOXD8 in an m⁶ dependent manner. Further, HOXD8 could transcriptionally activate ITGA5 and overexpressed ITGA5 up-regulated the CPT MSCs' osteogenic differentiation. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with METTL3. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these HOX-ITG members, and METTL3, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these HOX-ITG members along with METTL3.

Table 19 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 20 generated from analysis of the ranks in table

19. The table 19 shows rankings of HOX-ITG members w.r.t METTL3. HOXB7 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 19 (laplace), 986 (linear) and 1319 (rbf). HOXB13 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 838 (laplace) and 999 (rbf). HOXB3 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1344 (laplace), 879 (linear) and 975 (rbf). HOXA9 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1467 (laplace) and 1544 (linear). HOXB9 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 193 (linear) and 1141 (rbf). HOXB8 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 409 (linear) and 670 (rbf). ITGAE - METTL3 shows low ranking of 382 (laplace) and 1529 (rbf). ITGB3BP - METTL3 shows low ranking of 217 (linear) and 212 (rbf). ITGA9 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 354 (linear) and 409 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, HOXB5 ,HOXA11 and HOXB4 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with METTL3, before treatment.

RANKING HOX-ITG MEMBERS VS METTL3

RANKING OF HOX-ITG MEMBERS W.R.T METTL3			
	laplace	linear	rbf
HOXB7 - METTL3	19	986	1319
HOXB5 - METTL3	471	1773	2115
HOXB13 - METTL3	838	1658	999
HOXA11 - METTL3	926	1656	1843
HOXB4 - METTL3	1075	1933	1721
HOXB3 - METTL3	1344	879	975
HOXA9 - METTL3	1467	1544	1587
HOXB9 - METTL3	1978	193	1141
HOXB8 - METTL3	2610	409	670
ITGAE - METTL3	382	2474	1529
ITGB3BP - METTL3	2266	217	212
ITGA9 - METTL3	2494	354	409

Table 19: 2nd order interaction ranking between METTL3 VS HOX-ITG members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 19 graphically, with the following influences - • HOX members w.r.t METTL3 with METTL3 – > HOX-B7/B13/B3/A9/B9/B8 and • ITG members w.r.t METTL3 with METTL3 – > ITG-AE/B3BP/A9.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
HOX members w.r.t METTL3	
HOX-B7/B13/B3/A9/B9/B8	METTL3
ITG members w.r.t METTL3	
ITG-AE/B3BP/A9	METTL3

Table 20: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between METTL3 and HOX-ITG members.

2.1.11. METTL3 - IL

Xiao et al. [26] found that the expression level of METTL3 and methylation level of m⁶A in human endplate cartilage with different degrees of degeneration were different. They confirmed that METTL3 could promote cleavage of pri-miR-126-5p and form mature miR-126-5p by combining with DGCR8. Next, they found that miR-126-5p can play a significant role in IL-1 β induced degeneration of endplate chondrocytes. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with METTL3. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these IL members, and METTL3, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these IL members along with METTL3.

Table 21 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 22 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 21. The table 21 shows rankings of IL members w.r.t METTL3. IL17RD - METTL3 shows low ranking of 407 (laplace), 1569 (linear) and 1307 (rbf). IL17D - METTL3 shows low ranking of 645 (laplace), 445 (linear) and 183 (rbf). IL17RB - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1183 (linear) and 269 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, IL1RL2 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with METTL3, before treatment.

One can also interpret the results of the table 21 graphically, with the following influences - • IL members w.r.t METTL3 with METTL3 – > IL-17RD/17D/17RB.

2.1.12. METTL3 - KIF

Ma et al. [27] confirmed that KIF3C is highly expressed in prostate cancer (PCa) tissues and cell lines. Their hypothesis and experiments concluded that METTL3 induced m⁶A modification on KIF3C, promoting the stabilization of KIF3C-mRNA by IGF2 binding protein 1 (IGF2BP1). The prediction that miR-320d inhibits KIF3C expression by targeting METTL3 and thus inhibit the progression of PCa, was also confirmed experimentally. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with METTL3. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-

RANKING IL MEMBERS VS METTL3

RANKING OF IL MEMBERS W.R.T METTL3			
	laplace	linear	rbf
IL17RD - METTL3	407	1569	1307
IL17D - METTL3	645	445	183
IL1RL2 - METTL3	1602	1808	2197
IL17RB - METTL3	1852	1183	269

Table 21: 2nd order interaction ranking between METTL3 VS IL members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

IL members w.r.t METTL3	
IL-17RD/17D/17RB	METTL3

Table 22: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between METTL3 and IL members.

1922159, these KIF members, and METTL3, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these KIF members along with METTL3.

Table 23 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 24 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 23. The table 23 shows rankings of KIF members w.r.t METTL3. KIF9 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1302 (laplace), 1111 (linear) and 98 (rbf). KIF22 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1465 (laplace), 415 (linear) and 188 (rbf). KIF14 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 94 (linear) and 149 (rbf). KIF18B - METTL3 shows low ranking of 213 (linear) and 476 (rbf). KIF20B - METTL3 shows low ranking of 275 (linear) and 339 (rbf). KIF13A - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1142 (linear) and 1256 (rbf). KIF20A - METTL3 shows low ranking of 65 (linear) and 159 (rbf). KIFC1 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 292 (linear) and 89 (rbf). KIF2C - METTL3 shows low ranking of 114 (linear) and 135 (rbf). KIF4A - METTL3 shows low ranking of 111 (linear) and 454 (rbf). KIF15 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 37 (linear) and 44 (rbf). KIF23 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 3 (linear) and 333 (rbf). KIF18A - METTL3 shows low ranking of 265 (linear) and 83 (rbf). KIF11 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 60 (linear) and 139 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, KIF27 and KIF7 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with METTL3, before treatment.

RANKING KIF MEMBERS VS METTL3							
RANKING OF KIF MEMBERS W.R.T METTL3							
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
KIF27 - METTL3	654	2020	1642	KIF7 - METTL3	856	2648	2518
KIF9 - METTL3	1302	1111	98	KIF22 - METTL3	1465	415	188
KIF14 - METTL3	1671	94	149	KIF18B - METTL3	1737	213	476
KIF20B - METTL3	1859	275	339	KIF13A - METTL3	1873	1142	1256
KIF20A - METTL3	1956	65	159	KIFC1 - METTL3	1970	292	89
KIF2C - METTL3	2025	114	135	KIF4A - METTL3	2371	111	454
KIF15 - METTL3	2410	37	44	KIF23 - METTL3	2492	3	333
KIF18A - METTL3	2573	265	83	KIF11 - METTL3	2677	60	139

Table 23: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between METTL3 VS KIF members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 23 graphically, with the following influences - • KIF members w.r.t METTL3 with METTL3 – > KIF-9/22/14/18B/20B/13A/20A/C1/2C/4A/15/23/18A/11.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
KIF members w.r.t METTL3	
KIF-9/22/14/18B/20B/13A/20A	...
/C1/2C/4A/15/23/18A/11	METTL3

Table 24: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between METTL3 and KIF members.

2.1.13. METTL3 - LINC

Yan et al. [28] found that LINC00475 was overexpressed in gliomas. Mechanistically, METTL3 induced the generation of LINC00475-S by splicing LINC00475 through m⁶A modification and subsequently promotes mitochondrial fission in glioma cells by inhibiting the expression of MIF. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with METTL3. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these LINC members, and METTL3, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these LINC members along with METTL3.

Table 25 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 26 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 25. The table 25 shows rankings of LINC members w.r.t METTL3. LINC00261 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 204 (linear) and 117 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, LINC01106, LINC00338, LINC00888, LINC00858, LINC00242 and LINC01123 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with METTL3, before

treatment.

RANKING LINC MEMBERS VS METTL3			
RANKING OF LINC MEMBERS W.R.T METTL3			
	laplace	linear	rbf
LINC01106 - METTL3	377	2443	2200
LINC00338 - METTL3	1435	1810	1923
LINC00888 - METTL3	1526	2639	2637
LINC00261 - METTL3	2048	204	117
LINC00858 - METTL3	2052	2730	2313
LINC00242 - METTL3	2227	2064	2732
LINC01123 - METTL3	2422	1978	2054

Table 25: 2nd order interaction ranking between METTL3 VS LINC members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 25 graphically, with the following influences - • LINC members w.r.t METTL3 with METTL3 – > LINC00261.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
LINC members w.r.t METTL3	
LINC-00261	METTL3

Table 26: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between METTL3 and LINC members.

2.1.14. METTL3 - PARP

Chromatin remodeling and m⁶A modification are two layers that control gene expression and DNA damage signaling in most eukaryotic bio-processes. Sun et al. [29] report that PARP1 controls the chromatin accessibility of METTL3 to regulate its transcription and subsequent m⁶A methylation of poly(A)⁺ RNA in response to DNA damage induced by radiation. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with METTL3. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these PARP members, and METTL3, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these PARP members along with METTL3.

Table 27 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 28 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 27. The table 27 shows rankings of PARP members w.r.t METTL3. PARP16 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 533 (laplace) and 1018 (rbf). PARP1 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1415 (laplace), 431 (linear) and 288 (rbf). PARP2 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1092 (linear) and 806 (rbf). PARPBP - METTL3 shows low ranking of 131 (linear) and 120 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

RANKING PARP MEMBERS VS METTL3			
RANKING OF PARP MEMBERS W.R.T METTL3			
	laplace	linear	rbf
PARP16 - METTL3	533	2371	1018
PARP1 - METTL3	1415	431	288
PARP2 - METTL3	2165	1092	806
PARPBP - METTL3	2426	131	120

Table 27: 2nd order interaction ranking between METTL3 VS PARP members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 27 graphically, with the following influences - • PARP members w.r.t METTL3 with METTL3 – > PARP-16/1/2/BP.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
PARP members w.r.t METTL3	
PARP-16/1/2/BP	METTL3

Table 28: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between METTL3 and PARP members.

2.1.15. METTL3 - RBM

X chromosome inactivation in mammals is regulated by the non-coding (nc) RNA, XIST, which represses the chromosome from which it is transcribed. High levels of m⁶A RNA modification occur within XIST exon I, and in XIST exon VII. This m⁶A modification is catalysed by the METTL-3/14 complex that is directed to specific targets, by RBM-15/15B. m⁶A modification of XIST RNA has been reported to be important for XIST-mediated gene silencing. Coker et al. [30] show that in mouse embryonic stem cells (mESCs), RBM15 interacts with the m⁶A complex, the SETD1B histone

modifying complex, and several proteins linked to RNA metabolism. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with METTL3. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these RBM members, and METTL3, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these RBM members along with METTL3.

Table 29 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 30 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 29. The table 29 shows rankings of RBM members w.r.t METTL3. RBM28 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 201 (laplace), 857 (linear) and 1247 (rbf). RBMX - METTL3 shows low ranking of 562 (laplace), 688 (linear) and 633 (rbf). RBM26 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1251 (laplace), 1060 (linear) and 1080 (rbf). RBM19 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1349 (laplace), 736 (linear) and 862 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

RANKING RBM MEMBERS VS METTL3			
RANKING OF RBM MEMBERS W.R.T METTL3			
	laplace	linear	rbf
RBM28 - METTL3	201	857	1247
RBMX - METTL3	562	688	633
RBM26 - METTL3	1251	1060	1080
RBM19 - METTL3	1349	736	862

Table 29: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between METTL3 VS RBM members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 29 graphically, with the following influences - • RBM members w.r.t METTL3 with METTL3 – > RBM-28/X/26/19.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
RBM members w.r.t METTL3	
RBM-28/X/26/19	METTL3

Table 30: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between METTL3 and RBM members.

2.1.16. METTL3 - SLC7

Xu et al. [31] showed that the m⁶A and METTL3 were both elevated in lung adenocar-

cinoma (LUAD) patients and lung cancer cells. They found that METTL3 could lead to proliferation and inhibit ferroptosis in different LUAD cell models, while METTL3 knockdown suppressed LUAD growth. Further, SLC7A11 (the subunit of system Xc⁻), was identified as the direct target of METTL3 by mRNA-seq and MeRIP-seq. METTL3-mediated m⁶A modification stabilized SLC7A11 mRNA and promote its translation, thus promoting LUAD cell proliferation and inhibiting cell ferroptosis. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with METTL3. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these SLC7 members, and METTL3, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these SLC7 members along with METTL3.

Table 31 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 32 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 31. The table 31 shows rankings of SLC7 members w.r.t METTL3. SLC7A8 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1357 (linear) and 1014 (rbf). SLC7A2 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 138 (linear) and 318 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

RANKING SLC7 MEMBERS VS METTL3			
RANKING OF SLC7 MEMBERS W.R.T METTL3			
	laplace	linear	rbf
SLC7A8 - METTL3	2400	1357	1014
SLC7A2 - METTL3	2217	138	318

Table 31: 2nd order interaction ranking between METTL3 VS SLC7 members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 31 graphically, with the following influences - • SLC7 members w.r.t METTL3 with METTL3 - > SLC7-A8/A2.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
SLC7 members w.r.t METTL3	
SLC7-A8/A2	METTL3

Table 32: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between METTL3 and SLC7 members.

2.1.17. METTL3 - SNHG

Jian et al. [32] demonstrated that in MNNG-induced gastric cancer (GC) tumorigenesis, METTL3 facilitated cellular epithelial-mesenchymal transition and biological

functions through the m⁶A modification of downstream target SNHG7. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with METTL3. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these SNHG members, and METTL3, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these SNHG members along with METTL3.

Table 33 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 34 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 33. The table 33 shows rankings of SNHG members w.r.t METTL3. SNHG6 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 585 (laplace), 876 (linear) and 834 (rbf). SNHG5 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 665 (laplace), 665 (linear) and 471 (rbf). SNHG18 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 781 (laplace) and 1237 (linear). SNHG16 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 821 (laplace), 762 (linear) and 610 (rbf). SNHG10 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1024 (laplace), 880 (linear) and 635 (rbf). SNHG15 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1605 (laplace), 1091 (linear) and 822 (rbf). SNHG1 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1185 (linear) and 1154 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, SNHG17, SNHG7, SNHG8 and SNHG3 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with METTL3, before treatment.

RANKING SNHG MEMBERS VS METTL3			
RANKING OF SNHG MEMBERS W.R.T METTL3			
	laplace	linear	rbf
SNHG17 - METTL3	146	1722	1972
SNHG7 - METTL3	149	1950	1695
SNHG6 - METTL3	585	876	834
SNHG5 - METTL3	665	665	471
SNHG18 - METTL3	781	1237	1632
SNHG16 - METTL3	821	762	610
SNHG8 - METTL3	862	1642	1564
SNHG10 - METTL3	1024	880	635
SNHG3 - METTL3	1591	1630	769
SNHG15 - METTL3	1605	1091	822
SNHG1 - METTL3	2493	1185	1154

Table 33: 2nd order interaction ranking between METTL3 VS SNHG members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 33 graphically, with the following influences - • SNHG members w.r.t METTL3 with METTL3 – > SNHG-6/5/18/16/10/15/1.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

SNHG members w.r.t METTL3

SNHG-6/5/18/16/10/15/1 METTL3

Table 34: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between METTL3 and SNHG members.

2.1.18. METTL3 - TCF

Wang et al. [33] show that upregulated METTL3 promotes the progression of thyroid carcinoma through m⁶A methylation on TCF1 mRNA. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with METTL3. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these TCF members, and METTL3, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these TCF members along with METTL3.

Table 35 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 36 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 35. The table 35 shows rankings of TCF members w.r.t METTL3. TCF3 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 116 (laplace), 1430 (linear) and 1056 (rbf). TCF19 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 722 (laplace) and 1207 (linear) TCF7 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1500 (laplace) and 529 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, TCFL5 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with METTL3, before treatment.

RANKING TCF MEMBERS VS METTL3

RANKING OF TCF MEMBERS W.R.T METTL3

	laplace	linear	rbf
TCF3 - METTL3	116	1430	1056
TCF19 - METTL3	722	1207	1875
TCF7 - METTL3	1500	1621	529
TCFL5 - METTL3	2132	1744	2008

Table 35: 2nd order interaction ranking between METTL3 VS TCF members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 35 graphically, with the following influences - • TCF members w.r.t METTL3 with METTL3 – > TCF-6/5/18/16/10/15/1.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
TCF members w.r.t METTL3	
TCF-6/5/18/16/10/15/1	METTL3

Table 36: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between METTL3 and TCF members.

2.1.19. METTL3 - TGFB

In gastric cancer (GC), Yuan et al. [34] found that METTL3 could combine with p-SMAD3 to regulate the transcription of downstream target genes. TGF- β /B)/SMAD signaling is a complex regulatory network that both inhibits and promotes tumorigenesis. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with METTL3. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these TGFB members, and METTL3, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these TGFB members along with METTL3.

Table 37 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 38 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 37. The table 37 shows rankings of TGFB members w.r.t METTL3. TGFB1 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 349 (laplace), 461 (linear) and 1126 (rbf). TGFBRAP1 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 318 (linear) and 689 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, TGFB3 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with METTL3, before treatment.

RANKING TGFB MEMBERS VS METTL3			
RANKING OF TGFB MEMBERS W.R.T METTL3			
	laplace	linear	rbf
TGFB1 - METTL3	349	461	1126
TGFB3 - METTL3	913	2169	2414
TGFBRAP1 - METTL3	2336	318	689

Table 37: 2nd order interaction ranking between METTL3 VS TGFB members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 37 graphically, with the following influences - • TGFB members w.r.t METTL3 with METTL3 – > TGFB-1/RAP1.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

TGFB members w.r.t METTL3

TGFB-1/RAP1	METTL3
--------------------	---------------

Table 38: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between METTL3 and TGFB members.

2.1.20. METTL3 - TRIM

In osteosarcoma tissues, Zhou et al. [35] found TRIM7 expression to be upregulated which led to osteosarcoma cell migration and invasion through ubiquitination of breast cancer metastasis suppressor 1 (BRMS1). They also observed loss of TRIM7 m⁶A modification and reported that METTL3 and YTHDF2 were the main factors involved in the aberrant m⁶A modification of TRIM7. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with METTL3. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these TRIM members, and METTL3, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these TRIM members along with METTL3.

Table 39 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 40 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 39. The table 39 shows rankings of TRIM members w.r.t METTL3. TRIM7 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 108 (laplace), 1100 (linear) and 1128 (rbf). TRIM65 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 235 (laplace) and 853 (linear). TRIM32 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 346 (laplace), 1428 (linear) and 952 (rbf). TRIM59 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 549 (laplace), 897 (linear) and 528 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, TRIM28 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with METTL3, before treatment.

One can also interpret the results of the table 39 graphically, with the following influences - • TRIM members w.r.t METTL3 with METTL3 – > TRIM-7/65/32/59.

2.1.21. METTL3 - UBE2

In human pan-cancer analysis, Jiang et al. [36] found that UBE2C was elevated and its expression was markedly associated with tumor mutation burden (TMB), microsatellite instability (MSI), immune cell infiltration, and diverse drug sensitivities. They showed that the METTL3/SNHG1/miRNA-140-3p axis could potentially regulate UBE2C expression. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with METTL3. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these UBE2 members, and METTL3, were found to be down regulated and

RANKING TRIM MEMBERS VS METTL3			
RANKING OF TRIM MEMBERS W.R.T METTL3			
	laplace	linear	rbf
TRIM7 - METTL3	108	1100	1128
TRIM65 - METTL3	235	853	1578
TRIM32 - METTL3	346	1428	952
TRIM59 - METTL3	549	897	528
TRIM28 - METTL3	738	2147	1708

Table 39: 2nd order interaction ranking between METTL3 VS TRIM members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
TRIM members w.r.t METTL3	
TRIM-7/65/32/59	METTL3

Table 40: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between METTL3 and TRIM members.

their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these UBE2 members along with METTL3.

Table 41 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 42 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 41. The table 41 shows rankings of UBE2 members w.r.t METTL3. UBE2G2 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1041 (laplace) and 978 (rbf). UBE2T - METTL3 shows low ranking of 234 (linear) and 172 (rbf). UBE2C - METTL3 shows low ranking of 180 (linear) and 101 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, UBE2S showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with METTL3, before treatment.

One can also interpret the results of the table 41 graphically, with the following influences - • UBE2 members w.r.t METTL3 with METTL3 – > UBE2-G2/T/C.

2.1.22. METTL3 - USP

In osteosarcoma (OS), Wang et al. [37] USP13 was found to be upregulated and promote OS progression through regulating aerobic glycolysis. USP13 interacted with, deubiquitinated, and thus stabilized METTL3, leading to increased global m⁶A abundance in OS cells. Their results also showed that METTL3 could bind to m⁶A-modified

RANKING UBE2 MEMBERS VS METTL3			
RANKING OF UBE2 MEMBERS W.R.T METTL3			
	laplace	linear	rbf
UBE2S - METTL3	685	1570	2088
UBE2G2 - METTL3	1041	1953	978
UBE2T - METTL3	1878	234	172
UBE2C - METTL3	2528	180	101

Table 41: 2nd order interaction ranking between METTL3 VS UBE2 members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
UBE2 members w.r.t METTL3	
UBE2-G2/T/C	METTL3

Table 42: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between METTL3 and UBE2 members.

ATG5 mRNA, which is crucial for autophagosome formation, and inhibit ATG5 mRNA decay on an IGF2BP3 dependent manner, thereby promoting autophagy and the autophagy-associated malignancy of OS. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with METTL3. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these USP members, and METTL3, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these USP members along with METTL3.

Table 43 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 44 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 43. The table 43 shows rankings of USP members w.r.t METTL3. USP10 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 447 (laplace), 601 (linear) and 1202 (rbf). USP28 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1077 (laplace), 490 (linear) and 839 (rbf). USP39 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1533 (laplace), 188 (linear) and 325 (rbf). USP13 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 100 (linear) and 110 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, USP36 and USP1 showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with METTL3, before treatment.

One can also interpret the results of the table 43 graphically, with the following influences - • USP members w.r.t METTL3 with METTL3 – > USP-10/28/39/13.

RANKING USP MEMBERS VS METTL3			
RANKING OF USP MEMBERS W.R.T METTL3			
	laplace	linear	rbf
USP10 - METTL3	447	601	1202
USP28 - METTL3	1077	490	839
USP36 - METTL3	1350	1839	1591
USP1 - METTL3	1469	2265	1971
USP39 - METTL3	1533	188	325
USP13 - METTL3	2208	100	110

Table 43: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between METTL3 VS USP members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
USP members w.r.t METTL3	
USP-10/28/39/13	METTL3

Table 44: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between METTL3 and USP members.

2.1.23. METTL3 - ZBTB

Huang et al. [38] revealed the mechanism by which METTL3 regulated the stability and expression of ZBTB4 and the trophoblast migration ability of recurrent spontaneous abortion (RSA). These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with METTL3. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these ZBTB members, and METTL3, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of these ZBTB members along with METTL3.

Table 45 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 46 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 45. The table 45 shows rankings of ZBTB members w.r.t METTL3. ZBTB25 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 35 (laplace), 859 (linear) and 1321 (rbf). ZBTB39 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 106 (laplace) and 1093 (rbf). ZBTB2 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 529 (laplace), 945 (linear) and 919 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, ZBTB12, ZBTB24 and ZBTB9 showed high ranking and might not be

synergistically working with METTL3, before treatment.

RANKING ZBTB MEMBERS VS METTL3			
RANKING OF ZBTB MEMBERS W.R.T METTL3			
	laplace	linear	rbf
ZBTB25 - METTL3	35	859	1321
ZBTB39 - METTL3	106	1727	1093
ZBTB2 - METTL3	529	945	919
ZBTB12 - METTL3	924	2572	1982
ZBTB24 - METTL3	2360	1564	1878
ZBTB9 - METTL3	2711	1693	402

Table 45: 2nd order interaction ranking between METTL3 VS ZBTB members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 45 graphically, with the following influences - • ZBTB members w.r.t METTL3 with METTL3 – > ZBTB-10/28/39/13.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
ZBTB members w.r.t METTL3	
ZBTB-25/39/2	METTL3

Table 46: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between METTL3 and ZBTB members.

2.1.24. METTL3 - ZNF

Zhang et al. [39] found that ZNF740 enhances the invasive and proliferative capacity of liver cancer (hepatocellular carcinoma HCC) cells. Specific knockdown of ZNF740 inhibited HCC proliferation. ZNF740 enhanced the expression of the transcription factor METTL3 and promoted liver cancer cell proliferation in a METTL3-dependent manner. Further, METTL3 recruited YTHDF1 to regulate HIF1A mRNA stability. Thus, the ZNF740/METTL3/HIF1A signaling axis may facilitate the proliferation, invasion and metastasis of liver cancer via METTL3/HIF-1A signaling. These experimental studies confirm the existence of synergy between the above involved factors with METTL3. In colorectal cancer cells treated with ETC-1922159, these ZNF members, and METTL3, were found to be down regulated and their regulation was recorded independently. I was able to rank 2nd order combination of these ZNF members along with METTL3.

Table 47 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 48 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 47. The table 47 shows rankings of ZNF members w.r.t METTL3. ZNF639 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 33 (laplace), 1083 (linear) and 1178 (rbf). ZNF215 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 93 (laplace), 811 (linear) and 810 (rbf). ZNF428 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 329 (laplace), 1335 (linear) and 1239 (rbf). ZNF480 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 332 (laplace), 1508 (linear) and 1110 (rbf). ZNF614 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 481 (laplace), 1188 (linear) and 1122 (rbf). ZNF486 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 519 (laplace) and 1553 (linear) and 1685 ZNF37BP - METTL3 shows low ranking of 629 (laplace) and 1511 (linear) and 1912 ZNF793 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 677 (laplace) and 1395 (linear) ZNF263 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 776 (laplace), 344 (linear) and 148 (rbf). ZNF93 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 828 (laplace) and 1279 (linear) and ZNF629 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 895 (laplace), 935 (linear) and 699 (rbf). ZNF248 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1215 (laplace) and 1525 (linear) ZNF48 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1317 (laplace) and 1028 (linear) and ZNF367 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 152 (linear) and 433 (rbf). ZNF689 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 915 (linear) and 1354 (rbf). ZNF780B - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1483 (linear) and 1475 (rbf). ZNF740 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 917 (linear) and 1317 (rbf). ZNF789 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 786 (linear) and 821 (rbf). ZNF511 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 807 (linear) and 680 (rbf). ZNF74 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 913 (linear) and 673 (rbf). ZNF589 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1043 (linear) and 370 (rbf). ZNF330 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 1150 (linear) and 801 (rbf). ZNF485 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 452 (linear) and 199 (rbf). ZNF239 - METTL3 shows low ranking of 223 (linear) and 77 (rbf). These rankings point to the synergy existing between the two components, which have been down regulated after the drug treatment.

Further, ZNF775, ZNF22, ZNF771, ZNF124, ZNF146, ZNF275, ZNF202, ZNF572, ZNF691, ZNF343, ZNF584, ZNF670, ZNF738, ZNF232, ZNF32, ZNF273, ZNF138, ZNF620, ZNF90, ZNF174, ZNF502, ZNF815P, ZNF736, ZNF594, ZNF695, ZNF519, ZNF204P, ZNF346 and ZNF280D showed high ranking and might not be synergistically working with METTL3, before treatment.

One can also interpret the results of the table 47 graphically, with the following influences - ● ZNF members w.r.t METTL3 with METTL3 – > ZNF-639 / 215 / 428 / 480 / 614 / 486 / 37BP / 793 / 263 / 93 / 629 / 248 / 48 / 367 / 689 / 780B / 740 / 789 / 511 / 74 / 589 / 330 / 485 / 239.

3. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic METTL3 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of METTL3-X that might be prevalent in CRC cells after treatment with ETC-1922159 drug.

RANKING ZNF MEMBERS VS METTL3

RANKING OF ZNF MEMBERS W.R.T METTL3							
	laplace	linear	rbf		laplace	linear	rbf
ZNF639 - METTL3	33	1083	1178	ZNF215 - METTL3	93	811	810
ZNF428 - METTL3	329	1335	1239	ZNF480 - METTL3	332	1508	1110
ZNF775 - METTL3	390	2334	2402	ZNF22 - METTL3	472	1990	2536
ZNF614 - METTL3	481	1188	1122	ZNF771 - METTL3	490	2240	2148
ZNF486 - METTL3	519	1553	1685	ZNF124 - METTL3	534	2141	1640
ZNF146 - METTL3	590	1866	2242	ZNF37BP - METTL3	629	1511	1912
ZNF793 - METTL3	677	1395	2044	ZNF263 - METTL3	776	344	148
ZNF93 - METTL3	828	1279	1654	ZNF275 - METTL3	837	1755	1700
ZNF512 - METTL3	870	912	1383	ZNF629 - METTL3	895	935	699
ZNF202 - METTL3	905	1657	2359	ZNF572 - METTL3	918	2543	1898
ZNF691 - METTL3	1002	1952	1846	ZNF343 - METTL3	1063	2181	2291
ZNF584 - METTL3	1179	2715	2219	ZNF248 - METTL3	1215	1525	1517
ZNF670 - METTL3	1301	2287	2471	ZNF48 - METTL3	1317	1028	2081
ZNF738 - METTL3	1525	1707	1125	ZNF445 - METTL3	1534	569	964
ZNF232 - METTL3	1626	2055	2258	ZNF32 - METTL3	1706	1596	2722
ZNF273 - METTL3	1716	2570	2475	ZNF138 - METTL3	1722	2109	1813
ZNF367 - METTL3	1732	152	433	ZNF689 - METTL3	1736	915	1354
ZNF620 - METTL3	1760	2189	2416	ZNF90 - METTL3	1857	2315	1525
ZNF780B - METTL3	1864	1483	1475	ZNF740 - METTL3	2002	917	1317
ZNF174 - METTL3	2029	1939	1398	ZNF789 - METTL3	2046	786	821
ZNF502 - METTL3	2095	861	2192	ZNF511 - METTL3	2106	807	680
ZNF815P - METTL3	2119	2737	2729	ZNF736 - METTL3	2309	1976	2250
ZNF74 - METTL3	2328	913	673	ZNF589 - METTL3	2347	1043	370
ZNF330 - METTL3	2406	1150	801	ZNF594 - METTL3	2454	2568	1738
ZNF695 - METTL3	2533	1235	2590	ZNF519 - METTL3	2556	2336	2698
ZNF204P - METTL3	2580	2012	2112	ZNF346 - METTL3	2603	2409	1501
ZNF485 - METTL3	2626	452	199	ZNF280D - METTL3	2645	759	1770
ZNF239 - METTL3	2656	223	77				

Table 47: 2nd order interaction ranking between METTL3 VS ZNF members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

ZNF members w.r.t METTL3	
ZNF-639/215/428/480/614/486/37BP/793/263 ...	
93/629/248/48/367/689/780B/740/789/511/74 ...	
589/330/485/239	METTL3

Table 48: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between METTL3 and ZNF members.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Madan et al. [40].

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